

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE USE OF PROJECT IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: *The given article deals with the teaching methods of foreign languages. In particular, we focused on the project method in order to increase the motivation of school learners. There are five points that are universal and applicable to any project. Also, there are given some recommendations in order to perform project work in oral or written form.*

Keywords: *project, foreign language, motivation, school learners, technology.*

Introduction: Increasing requirements for communicative knowledge of a foreign language makes it necessary to look for new forms and methods of teaching to increase the motivation of school learners. Currently, innovative teachers pay great attention to the principles of a student-centered approach, in which the personality of the learner is at the center of learning. The process of humanization of education and upbringing, associated with increased attention to the personality of the child, with an approach to him as the highest value of society, reflects the social order that, on the threshold of the third millennium, society imposes on educational systems of different levels.

Now many developed countries of the world have realized the need to reform their educational systems so that the focus of teachers is the learners' cognitive activity. What is important is not the end result (knowledge becomes obsolete, subject to change), but the process of acquiring knowledge. It is necessary to teach students to learn independently and acquire the necessary knowledge, to teach them the ability to adapt to life situations and make decisions independently, and think critically. With the traditional approach and traditional teaching aids, these tasks were quite difficult to solve. A person-oriented approach (it can be called developing, or humanistic) is able to positively solve the above problems.

The pedagogical technologies of this approach include the method of projects, as well as learning in collaboration, non-traditional forms of lessons and a communicative approach to teaching foreign languages. Thus, the project method, which is quite actively used abroad in teaching foreign languages, has only recently begun to be used in the domestic education system.

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In connection with the sociolinguistic approach to teaching a foreign language, this method provides a real opportunity to form not only communicative but also linguistic and regional and methodological competence of students. The idea of collaborative learning (as well as its varieties) arose at the beginning of the century in the writings of American educators-researchers E. Parkhurst (“Dalton Plan”), J. Devay, and W. Kilpatrick (“project method”). This idea runs like a red thread through the activities of the French teacher S. Frenet, who sought to combine individual work and group work so that one type of activity was not the main one in relation to others.

Theoretical and technological aspects of developmental education are associated with the names of Sh.A. Amonashvili, L.S. Vygotsky, V.V. Davidova, L.V. Zankova, D.B. Elkonina and others. Innovative teachers note that project-based learning significantly increases the motivation of students because makes the types of educational work more dynamic and opens up freedom for the activities of teachers. Maybe that is why it was foreign language teachers who first of all adopted the ideas of the project methodology: its goals and objectives are most closely related to the goals and objectives of the communicative approach, where the concepts of “active”, “activity” are the main ones, and linguistic equipment is put at the service of communicative skills and abilities. The barrier between teaching the theoretical foundations of the language (for example, vocabulary, grammar) and the practical application of the acquired knowledge is being erased.

A project is a work independently planned and implemented by schoolchildren, in which verbal communication is woven into the intellectual and emotional context of other activities. E.N. Polat emphasizes that the project method is based on the development of students' cognitive skills, the ability to independently construct their knowledge and navigate the information space, as well as the development of critical thinking [1; 15].

The following typology of projects can be proposed: - single-disciplinary (a project within one subject), - interdisciplinary (concerns all subjects, some subjects, for two subjects). By terms, projects can be: - large (for a year, for an academic quarter), - small (for a certain period of time, for example, for a week, where the main goal is communicative and linguistic). The project can be: - open (for several classes and have access outside the school), - closed (for one class). It is possible to distinguish: - the main project, - the subproject. The development of a pedagogical project involves mastering a number of operations, of which five points are universal and applicable to any project:

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- The genesis of a project (idea), leading to the adoption of certain decisions. It is important that the idea of the project meets the interests of all participants. The content of the project should be based on the life experience of the learner, work on the project involves the development of this experience.
- Formulation of the project (main idea, problems, goals). Distribution of responsibilities for project implementation.
- Joint activities for the implementation of the project, where the actions of learners are combined, and cooperation in groups.
- Presentation of the project in a predetermined form: defense, exhibition, publication, competition, etc.
- Reflection phase. Comprehension of the work done occurs at two levels: teacher and student. Self-assessment of the results and the process of individual and collective creativity, analysis of personal attitude to project work.

Project management sometimes requires the teacher to have qualities that differ from those that are presented to the teacher in the traditional education system.

To be a good project manager, you need to master the “technology” of training, be a professional in your field, be organized yourself and be able to organize others, be always ready for the role of a subordinate, have a developed sense of foresight, be able to act as an intermediary, be able to leave your leadership role to become a participant in the process. It is possible to talk about the project only if the students have moved from the status of passive learners to a level where they themselves are actors and creators of their own learning. There is a shift in emphasis from the result to the process itself, which gives children joy, “the luxury of human communication.” It is this aspect that cannot be neglected, especially when teaching foreign languages, where they constantly talk about motivation, often without knowing how to create it.

In pedagogical practice, the project method is aimed at realizing the creative potential of the learner, creativity, non-standard thinking, at developing their mental activity, and teaches the selection and analysis of information. Mastering a foreign language in the process of project work gives school learners the true joy of learning, and introduces them to a new culture. When performing project work in oral or written form, it is necessary to adhere to some recommendations.

First, since project work gives learners the opportunity to express their own ideas, it is important not to overtly control and regulate learners, it is desirable to encourage their independence.

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Secondly, the design work is mostly open, so there can be no clear plan for its implementation. In the process of performing design assignments, some additional material can also be introduced.

Third, most projects can be done by individual learners, but a project will be most creative if done in groups. This is especially important, for example, when selecting pictures for collages and other work of this kind. Some projects are done independently at home, some of the project tasks take part of the lesson, and others take the whole lesson. How the project is carried out and presented is important.

Projects can be done on separate sheets and stapled together to form a montage, exhibition or book of the most interesting travel stories, your favorite pets, your city, and more. Groups can compete with each other. The project methodology uses all the best ideas developed by traditional and modern methods of teaching foreign languages. First of all, they include diversity, problems, learning with pleasure and the so-called ego factor [2; 3].

Variety, a necessary feature of any good learning, helps keep learning interesting. Problematic means that learners use the language to complete tasks that are characterized by the novelty of the result and new ways of achieving it. Of course, it is important that the learner studies with pleasure. A teenager learns productively and learns a lot if he learns freely, without coercion, and experiences joy. Of particular importance is the ego factor, that is, the ability to talk about what schoolchildren think, about their thoughts. The work on the project is combined with the creation of a solid language base for the trainees.

The project methodology in teaching a foreign language also teaches independent work, it is here that it plays a leading role. As a result of this approach, learners will be armed with methodological tools for further improvement of skills and abilities in a foreign language.

The purpose of this technique is to introduce a new stream into the teaching of foreign languages, use active teaching methods, develop the initiative and independence of students in the implementation of communication in the target language, and broaden their horizons when solving various cognitive tasks. This method involves the rejection of traditional textbooks, the development of free self-expression and learners' creativity, and the formation of genuine communicative competence. The advantages of this technique are that it is aimed at the student as a person, taking into account his interests, age, and subjective experience. Group forms of work are used, which develop the ability to work in a team. In addition to applying

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previously mastered linguistic knowledge and acquiring new linguistic knowledge, work on this method aims students to use knowledge from other academic subjects.

The implementation of the ideas of the project methodology should be based on the mobilization of the creative abilities and personal potential of children. Project work develops learners' independence. On the other hand, the project itself is the result of a large independent work of learners. For example, with primary learners, you can start two projects – “Book about myself” and “Family album”. Children start two albums. In one they paste their photos. In the other - photos of members of his family. Second-graders are given the task to tell about themselves, and their family, building the simplest sentences [3; 10].

Conclusion: Learners, showing albums, comment on their content. It is important to note that in the course of work on these projects, the most important educational task is solved - respect for family traditions. Thus, by changing the content and form, one should ensure that these elements are still attractive to learners and remain the “bright spot” of the lesson.

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